

Solving combined economic emission dispatch problem of power system including PV generation

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Abstract. This paper deals with dynamic combined economic emission dispatch problem of an electric power system consisting of thermal, hydro and photovoltaic (PV) power plants. Mathematical models of these plants as well as the model of dynamic combined economic-environmental nonlinear optimization problem are given. The proposed optimization model was implemented in publicly available GAMS software, and the result is the optimal load distribution among the plants during a one-day optimization period. The software is applied to the power system without PV power plants and with a number of new PV plants added to the existing hydrothermal system. The results quantify the positive effects of PV power plants on both fuel cost and greenhouse gas reduction and recommendations are given related to the application of PV generation in modern systems. Software efficiency in solving both dynamic economic dispatch (DED) and dynamic combined economic emission dispatch (DCEED) problems is discussed, and the conclusions are drawn about its application possibilities.

1 Introduction

Today, humanity faces challenges of rapidly depleting fuel reserves, environmental concerns, and the demands of an ever-increasing population. Therefore, a lot of research has been done in order to meet increased electricity demand, to reduce the extensive use of fossil fuels and to contribute to economic growth [1, 2]. These two goals imply the development of renewable energy sources (RES) and their application in efficient energy systems capable of providing safe and reliable power supply to all consumers. Further implementation of RES is encouraged by [3] with the aim of making the European Union climate neutral in 2050. To achieve this ambitious aim much work has been done throughout the Europe, including modernization of education in terms of RES and sustainability [4].

The application of RES causes the changes in both electric power system operation and planning. Therefore, modifications in formulation of mathematical problems regarding system operation and planning and appropriate problem-solving procedures are needed [5, 6]. One of the important problems of short-term operation planning is economic dispatch

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(ED). Generally, it is a nonlinear optimization problem that aims to allocate power to generating units, so that operating costs are minimized while ensuring the operation of a system in a safe and high-quality manner [7]. The dominant part of operating costs that strongly influences the price of electricity, is fuel costs of thermal generating units, and therefore they should be reduced. Nowadays, the energy crises and the environmental issue – emission of greenhouse gases due to operation of thermal power plants (TPPs), are the reasons to apply combined economic emission dispatch (CEED). The objective function of CEED minimizes both operating costs and the emissions [1, 8-10].

Economic dispatch is an old problem of how to coordinate the operation of power plants a day-ahead, and in real-time. Therefore, many approaches to the problem of ED can be found in published references. For example, ED of systems with thermal and hydropower plants (HPPs) is described in [7]. Possible modifications and extensions of the model of hydro-thermo coordination (HTC), including e.g. security constraints, prohibited operating zones, incorporation of renewable energy sources, energy storage systems and environmental concerns, are explained in [11] and [12].

The group of references that discuss the inclusion of solar power plants (SPPs) in thermal or hydrothermal power systems emphasize the crucial influence of solar irradiation and ambient temperature on energy production of these plants. Some studies assume that the available power of solar power plants can be predicted exactly, and deterministic approach to modelling of PV panels is applied [1, 10, 13]. These models regard to be simplified since they do not take into account uncertainty of the production, while in [14, 15] electricity production uncertainty is modelled by probability functions. The cost of solar generation is named per unit cost [13], or direct cost of solar PV power [8].

The reduction of greenhouse gas emissions is the essential issue of the application of SPPs, and the combined economic emission dispatch is commonly used for power systems including photovoltaic (PV) generation. Therefore, the objective function of CEED consisting of operating costs of the power plants, is extended with an added term describing the increase of the costs due to the total harmful gases emission above its allowed limit by introducing the appropriate tax, i.e. penalty factor [10]. In some references, this cost is increased by: the penalty cost or underestimation cost, and the reserve requirement cost or overestimation cost [9].

In general, economic dispatch problem of an electric power system is a complex high dimensional nonlinear optimization problem with multiple constraints and it normally requires the application of expensive commercial software packages. For educational and research purposes in higher education institutions it is desirable to apply alternative cheap or free software that enables studying economic dispatch through demonstrations and solution discussions for different compositions of generation units and objective functions.

In this paper, short-term economic dispatch and economic emission dispatch problems of hydro-thermo system without and with PV generation are solved using publicly available software GAMS (General Algebraic Modeling System) [16]. The theoretical basis consisting of mathematical models of thermal, hydro and solar power plants, as well as the optimization model of considered dispatch problem, are presented in Section 2 and Section 3, respectively. Section 4 discusses the results of GAMS application in solving dispatch problems in the electric power systems consisting of different combinations of generation units. Section 5 concludes the paper and provides the directions for further research.

2 Power plant models in ED problem

2.1 Model of thermal power plants

For ED problem solving, each thermal unit in TPPs is modelled by a cost function taking into account generated power limits. A cost function of thermal units is commonly approximated by fuel costs, while operations and maintenance costs are neglected. Thus, the cost function C_n , of thermal unit n , in monetary units per hour [MU/h], is modelled by second order polynomial [7]:

$$C_n(P_{Tn})=a_nP_{Tn}^2+b_nP_{Tn}+c_n, \tag{1}$$

where: P_{Tn} is the generated power in MW, and a_n , b_n and c_n are the coefficients in MU/(MW)²h, MU/MWh and MU/h, respectively, of unit n of total N_T thermal units in an electric power system.

During the optimization period, the generated power of each thermal unit should be within the range between minimum and maximum power limits, P_{Tn}^{min} and P_{Tn}^{max} , respectively. Also, the limits of dynamic ramp-rate are specified: upper ramp-rate limit, RU_n , for increasing, and down ramp-rate limit, RD_n , for decreasing generation, of n^{th} thermal unit.

2.2 Model of hydropower plants

The model of HPPs for ED problem formulation includes operating costs proportional to the generated power of hydropower unit, P_{Hn} :

$$C_n(P_{Hn})=\zeta P_{Hn}. \tag{2}$$

In (2) C_n denotes operating costs in MU/h of the unit n of total N_H hydro units in an electric power system, and ζ denotes relative operating costs of the hydropower unit in MU/MWh. The generated power of each hydropower plant is the function of reservoir storage volume, V_n , and water discharge rate, Q_m [12]:

$$P_{Hn}=c_1^n(V_n)^2+c_2^n(Q_m)^2+c_3^nQ_mV_n+c_4^nV_n+c_5^nQ_m+c_6^n, \quad n=1, \dots, N_H, \tag{3}$$

where coefficients c_1^n , c_2^n , ..., c_6^n represent characteristic factors of n^{th} hydro unit. In ED problem solving, (3) is calculated in each time interval, i , of the optimization period T .

Further, in power system with coupled HPPs, water balance equation takes into account both downstream and upstream hydro units [17]:

$$V_n(j)=V_n(j-1)+t_j(Q_{dn}(j)-(Q_m(j)-Q_{pn}(j)))+\eta t_j \sum_{m \in U_m} (Q_{tm}(j-\tau_m)+Q_{pm}(j-\tau_m)), \tag{4}$$

within T , consisting of J equal time intervals with a duration of t_j [h]. The volume of reservoir storage of n^{th} hydro unit in j^{th} and time interval $j-1$ is $V_n(j)$ and $V_n(j-1)$, respectively, in m³. The rate of discharge, spillage and inflow of water of n^{th} hydro unit in a time interval j , is $Q_m(j)$, $Q_{pn}(j)$ and $Q_{dn}(j)$, respectively, in m³/h. The number of upstream hydro units that are just above n^{th} unit is U_m . The rate of discharge and spillage of water of m^{th} unit ($m \in U_m$) in j^{th} time interval is $Q_{tm}(j)$ and $Q_{pm}(j)$, respectively. Time lag of the rate of discharge and spillage of water from the upstream hydro units flowing into the downstream

plant is denoted by τ_m , while the losses of water are taken into account by the loss coefficient, η .

In each time interval of the optimization period, following limitations should be met:

- The volume of reservoir storage of each hydropower unit is between its minimum and maximum volume, V_n^{min} and V_n^{max} , respectively. Initial, V_n^{ini} , and final, V_n^{fin} , reservoir storage volumes, at the beginning and at the end of optimization period, respectively, are predetermined.
- Output power limitations of n^{th} hydropower unit, is between its minimum, P_{Hn}^{min} , and maximum, P_{Hn}^{max} , power.
- Rate of hourly water discharge of each hydropower unit is between its minimum, Q_{in}^{min} , and maximum, Q_{in}^{max} , discharge rate.

2.3 Model of solar power plants

The cost of power generated in a solar power plant, C_S , when the status of the plant is 1 (on) [1], is proportional to per unit cost of the production of this plant, C_{pus} :

$$C_S = C_{pus} P_S \quad (5)$$

The power generated by solar power plant, P_S , can be expressed as a function of ambient temperature, T_a , and incident solar radiation, H_i , as presented in [13] which introduces deterministic approach to PV power modelling:

$$P_S = P_r \{ 1 + (T_r - T_a) \cdot \eta_i \} H_i / 1000 \quad (6)$$

In (6), P_r , T_r and η_i are rated power, reference temperature and temperature coefficient, respectively. Incorporating stochastic models or probabilistic methods for solar power generation [14, 15] could better reflect real-world conditions, but these will be included in further research by the authors.

3 Model of dynamic combined economic emission problem

Dynamic combined economic emission dispatch (DCEED) problem can be described by a multi-objective function. General form of this function encompasses the costs of generated power in all N power generating units and the cost of emissions of harmful gases in considered electric power system. It should be minimized within the optimization period of one day consisting of $J = 24$ equal time intervals with the duration of $t_j = 1$ h:

$$\min C = \min \{ \sum_{j=1, 2, \dots, J} t_j \sum_{i=1, 2, \dots, N} (C_i(P_i(j)) + E_i(P_i(j))) \} \quad (7)$$

In power system consisting of N generation units: N_T thermal, N_H hydro and N_S solar power plants, (1), (2) and (5) are used, respectively, to calculate $C_i(P_i(j))$, i.e. the cost of generated power of each unit in considered time interval. The harmful gases are produced by thermal power plants and they depend on the generated power in j^{th} time interval. Therefore, the cost of gas emissions, $E_i(P_i(j))$, is expressed in MU/h:

$$E_i(P_i(j)) = C_e (d_i P_i(j))^2 + e_i P_i(j) + f_i \quad (8)$$

where C_e is a price of environmental pollution, i.e. penalty factor, and d_i , e_i and f_i are the coefficients of fuel emission, of i^{th} power unit [12].

In the model described in this paper, in each time interval of optimization period, the constraints to be satisfied are:

- The balance of active power in electric power system – the generation of all power units is equal to the sum of system load and transmission losses.
- Output powers of thermal units are between their minimum and maximum limits.
- Upper and down ramp-rate limits of thermal units are specified.
- Water balance equations are satisfied.
- Operational constraints and reservoir storage volumes of hydropower units are determined.

This list can be expanded with spinning reserve constraints, emission constraints e.g. the limitation of the environmental pollution or the limitation of the emission from each generating unit, transmission line constraints, etc.

4 Solving DCEED problem

4.1 Applied software and input data

The software applied to solve the problem of dynamic CEED is the software package GAMS intended for solving large dimensional optimization problems [16]. Its syntax is designed to enable simple encoding of the problems, while available built-in solvers are intended for solving different types of problems. Thus, GAMS enables engineers and researchers to solve the optimization problems without knowledge of the details of solution algorithms.

Four examples of electric power system were considered to investigate the effects of PV power plants on operating costs and total harmful gases emission:

- HTPS – hydrothermal power system with 5 TPPs and 4 reservoir HPPs [12].
- HTPS+1SPP – it is HTPS with added solar power plant of rated power 300 MW, assumed to be located nearby the capital of Serbia, Belgrade (44.85 N, 20.46 E).
- HTPS+2SPP – the system HTPS+1SPP with one more solar power plant of 300 MW located in the area of the city of Niš (43.33 N, 21.90 E).
- HTPS+3SPP – the system HTPS+2SPP with third solar power plant of 250 MW added, located nearby the city of Vranje (42.57 N, 21.90 E).

The example of hydrothermal power system and relevant parameters of all nine power plants were taken from [12], as well as 24-hour load demand of the system. Minor modifications were inserted related to minimum generated powers of TPP 1 and TPP 2, and their modified values are 125 MW and 165 MW, respectively. Also, maximum generated powers of TPP 1 and TPP 2 were set to 500 MW. Ambient temperature and incident solar radiation, necessary for the calculation of power generated by solar power plants (6), were obtained from [18], and data for summer solstice (21th June 2019) when the sky was clear was selected to better illustrate the effects of SPP applications. Temperature coefficient, reference temperature and per unit cost of solar-generated power were taken from [13] and [9]. Therefore, the research presented in the paper uses data from the literature and provides a basis for further work that would include a real-world case study and model validation using actual power system data.

Models of power plants and their parameters, load demand data and model of dynamic CEED were entered in the GAMS software, aiming to distribute the load among the units over 24-hour horizon to fulfil the objective function (7) while the constraints are satisfied. Thus, GAMS model represents a nonlinear programming model and appropriate built-in solver CONOPT was used.

4.2 Analysis of the results

For better insight into the influence of PV generation on operating costs and the emission of harmful gases, the results of GAMS code executions are expressed in relative units. Thus, the value of 1.00 pu is assigned to the operating costs of HTPS (which are 670752.87 MU in absolute units). After adding one, two and three solar power plants to the initial electric power system, the operating costs are reduced by 3%, 5% and 8% respectively. In other words, operating costs for HTPS, HTPS+1SPP, HTPS+2SPP and HTPS+3SPP, are 1.00 pu, 0.97 pu, 0.95 pu and 0.92 pu, respectively.

Emissions of greenhouse gasses, obtained by solving the DCEED and DED problems of all considered power systems, are also expressed in relative units and shown in Fig. 1. Relative emission values were calculated based on greenhouse gas emissions in the case of HTPS when the DCEED problem was solved. In this case the emissions are $16.32 \cdot 10^6$ kg in absolute units, i.e. 1.00 pu in relative units. The emissions in systems: HTPS+1SPP, HTPS+2SPP and HTPS+3 SPP when the DCEED problem is solved, are reduced to 0.79 pu, 0.64 pu and 0.55 pu, respectively. It indicates that operation of the PV plants in the power system contributes to a dramatic reduction in emissions of harmful gases.

Further, the importance of using a multi-objective function (7) is investigated, which involves minimizing operating costs and the cost of harmful gas emissions. For this purpose, the second term of the objective function (7) is neglected and the modified objective function with the constraints specified in Section 3, represents the formulation of the DED problem. GAMS software is applied to solve DED problems and the results are analysed. The following major gas emissions in the considered power systems HTPS, HTPS+1SPP, HTPS+2SPP and HTPS+3SPP were obtained and shown in Fig.1: 1.70 pu, 1.52 pu, 1.29 pu and 1.00 pu, respectively. These values indicate that the application of DCEED is very important in up-to-date power systems.

Fig. 1. Emissions of greenhouse gasses: EmissionsDCEED and EmissionsDED, for considered power systems, when the DCEED and DED problems were solved, respectively.

4.3 Software efficiency

It should be noted that GAMS proved to be effective for solving dynamic combined economic emission dispatch problems on commonly used PC computer. It was the fastest in solving the problem of DCEED on the example of HTPS when the solver CONOPT

execution time was 0.125 s although the model in GAMS code had 507 variables and needed 34 iterations to find the solution. This execution time did not exceed 0.2 s in all other examined cases, while the time for model solving and creation and reading/writing files was longer, but always less than 3.6 s. It proves that deterministic Nonlinear Programming (NLP) solver CONOPT, which is convenient for smooth nonlinear models [16], is efficient in solving DCEED problems.

Three more built-in optimization solvers were tested for benchmarking: IPOPT – Interior Point Optimizer for large scale NLP specialized for large smooth nonlinear problems, SNOPT - large scale Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) based NLP solver and MINOS – NLP solver which uses reduced gradient method. All three solvers were applied to solve DCEED problems and yielded the same results as obtained by CONOPT.

When solvers IPOPT and SNOPT were applied, the execution times were short and did not exceed 0.4 s and 0.6 s, respectively. Total time needed to solve the model, and create, read and write files was less than 4.1 s in all examined cases, indicating that solvers IPOPT and SNOPT are also efficient in solving addressed DCEED problems. On the other hand, solver MINOS was much slower than CONOPT, IPOPT and SNOPT, and therefore it is not recommended for problems which are more complex than problems solved in this paper. Namely, MINOS needed up to 16 s just for model solving, and less or equal to 19.1 s for both creating and reading/writing files.

5 Conclusion

This paper deals with a problem of dynamic combined economic emission dispatch of the electric power systems including PV generation. DCEED problem of systems without and with PV generation is solved by publicly available GAMS software. The positive influence of PV generation on both operating costs and greenhouse gas emissions is quantified, which leads to the conclusion that the application of PV generation in modern power systems is highly desirable. It was also found that solutions to the DCEED problem lead to a significant reduction in harmful gas emissions compared to the results of DED, in all considered power systems. GAMS software proved to be very efficient in solving economic dispatch problems and can be used as a tool for studying and research the coordination of engaged units in electric power systems. Further research will encompass the integration of other renewable energy source into the system, stochastic nature of their energy production, and energy storage systems, in solving DCEED problems. The model will be validated by using real grid data from an existing power system.

This work was supported by TRANSIT - Transition to Sustainable Future through Training and Education project under EU Horizon Grant No. 101075747 and by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia [Grant Number: 451-03-136/2025-03/200102]. For the purpose of open access, the author(s) has applied a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license to any Author Accepted Manuscript version arising.

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